

AQUASERV DMP_FROST

Version 1

Description

The FROST project aims to develop cryopreservation protocols for 10 species of microalgae (Order: Eustigmatales). The data collected will include:

Experimental parameters (e.g., cryoprotectant types, concentrations, equilibration times), Post-thaw viability metrics (e.g., survival rates, photosynthetic efficiency, cell morphology), Culture regrowth results, Microscopic images , Statistical analyses of experimental outcomes, Protocol documentation.

This data will support reproducible scientific research and will be shared for reuse by the scientific and aquaculture communities.

Funder

Grant

Researchers

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(0000-0001-8829-360X)

Organizations

Universidade de Vigo

1. Main Info

Title of Plan: [AQUASERV DMP_FROST](#)

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Organizations:

[Universidade de Vigo](#)

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Access: [Public](#)

2. Ethics

Introduction:

No personal, human, or animal data is involved.

Data sharing will not violate confidentiality, IP, or third-party rights.

3. Dataset descriptions

Introduction:

The FROST project aims to develop cryopreservation protocols for 10 species of microalgae (Order: Eustigmatales). The data collected will include:

- Experimental parameters (e.g., cryoprotectant types, concentrations, equilibration times)
- Post-thaw viability metrics (e.g., survival rates, photosynthetic efficiency, cell morphology)
- Culture regrowth results
- Microscopic images
- Statistical analyses of experimental outcomes
- Protocol documentation and metadata
- This data will support reproducible scientific research and will be shared for reuse by the scientific and aquaculture communities.

Descriptions

[AQUASERV](#) | [FROST](#)

Template: [AQUASERV](#) | [all categories](#) | [generic template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

No

1.1.4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

We are not sure.

1.1.5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Produced by the FROST project.

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

2.1.1 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

Not sure where.

2.1.2 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

No

2.1.3 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Microalgae, Cryopreservation, Biobanking.

2.1.4 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

No

2.2 Making data accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Not 100% sure but probably IMIS or the Uvigo repository.

2.2.1.2 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

We are still working on it.

2.2.1.3 Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

We expect to get a DOI for the datasets.

2.2.2 Data

2.2.2.2 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

No embargo needed.

2.2.2.4 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

No

2.2.3 Metadata

2.2.3.2 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

I don't know.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Yes, we will follow IMIS standards.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology,

codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

No needed.

2.4.2 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Academic Free License 3.0.

3 Data security

3.1 Data security

3.1.1 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Yes, cloud storage

3.1.2 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

4 Other research outputs

4.1 Making other research outputs findable, including provisions for metadata

4.1.1 Will other research outputs be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

5 Allocation of resources

5.1 Allocation of resources

5.1.2 How will these be covered?

Provided by University for free.

5.1.3 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Alba Lago (0000-0002-5323-8165)

6 Ethics

6.1 Ethics

6.1.1 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No

6.1.2 Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No

7 Other issues

7.1 Other issues

7.1.1 Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

No

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